

VISCOSITY OF THORIUM ARSENATE GELS DURING SETTING

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The viscosities of thorium arsenate gel-forming mixtures have been measured during setting, using different amounts of the constituents of the gel-forming mixtures, and adding of extra amounts of electrolytes and non-electrolytes at different temperatures. The viscosity-time curves are either rapidly rising ones or are S-shaped. The viscosity at a certain time decreases with (i) an increase of thorium ions in the gel-forming mixture, (ii) the addition of non-electrolytes, and (iii) the increase of temperature. But it increases with increase in the amount of arsenic acid and with the addition of extra amounts of electrolytes.

Viscosity changes in a number of gels during the process of setting have been studied in this laboratory (Prasad and Modak, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1940, **11A**, 282). In the present investigation the viscosity of thorium arsenate gels has been measured at different temperatures using different amounts of the constituents of the gel-forming mixtures in presence and absence of extra amounts of electrolytes and non-electrolytes.

Gels of thorium arsenate were prepared for the first time by Prakash and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 587) in an opaque or translucent state from solutions of potassium arsenate and thorium nitrate. Prasad and Desai (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1938, **7**, III, 132) found that transparent gels of thorium arsenate are obtained if a solution of arsenic acid is used instead of that of potassium arsenate.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The apparatus (constant = 0.0021) used was the same as employed by Prasad and Modak (*loc. cit.*) and the experimental procedure was also the same.

Solutions Used.—Thorium nitrate (6 g.) was dissolved in redistilled water and the solution made upto 100 c.c., thoria content of which was found to be 2.82%.

Merck's extra pure pyro-arsenic acid (10 g.) was dissolved in 100 c.c. of the solution, As_2O_3 content of which was found to be 7.44%.

Different volumes of the solutions of the two substances along with the addition agents were made to 5 c.c. each, so that after mixing, the total volume of the mixture was always 10 c.c.

RESULTS.

The results obtained are shown graphically in the following figures in which the viscosity of the gel-forming mixtures, expressed in poise (absolute units) are plotted against different intervals of time, expressed in minutes, at which after the gel-formation has commenced, the viscosity readings were taken.

Fig. 1 gives the effect of the addition of different amounts of thorium nitrate (Q) to 0.051 c.c. of the arsenic acid solution at 35°.

Fig. 2 gives the effect of the addition of different amounts of arsenic acid (X) to 5.0 c.c. of thorium nitrate solution at 35°.

Fig. 3 gives the effect of temperature on the mixture containing 5.0 c.c. of thorium nitrate solution and 0.55 c.c. of the arsenic acid solution.

FIG. 1.

Effect of thorium ions.

Fig. 4 gives the viscosity-time curves at 35° of gels prepared from different volumes of potassium arsenate solution (12 g. per 100 c.c.) and 9 c.c. of the thorium nitrate solution. On mixing the above-named constituents a precipitate was first formed and it slowly disappeared. The gels formed were turbid. The precipitate reappeared after some time when the readings had to be stopped.

DISCUSSION.

It appears that the general nature of most of the curves shown in Figures 1-4 is essentially the same. All of them at first rise slowly, then

rapidly and in the end most of them tend to run parallel to the axis of viscosity and the others tend to become S-shaped. The absence of any discontinuity in the curves indicates that the various stages involved in the process of the formation of gels do not show their distinct existence. Evidently these stages run simultaneously and lend an aspect of continuity to the whole process of gelation. These conclusions are in conformity with those made by previous workers (Prasad, Modak, Mehta and Desai, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, **36**, 1384, 1938; Mehta, Parmar and Prasad, *loc. cit.*). On plotting $\log(\eta - \eta_0)$ against $\log t$, where η is the viscosity at time t and η_0 , the viscosity extrapolated from the curves for t equal to zero, the curves obtained are not straight lines, but when values of $\log(\eta - \eta_0)$ are plotted against t straight lines are obtained. This shows that the viscosity of thorium arsenate gel-forming mixtures changes with time in the same manner as found by Mardles (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1923, **18**, 327) in the case of gels of methylcellulose in benzyl alcohol.

FIG. 2.
Effect of arsenic acid.

The rate of change of viscosity with time is greatly altered by a change in the amount of the constituents of the gel-forming mixtures. With an increase in the amount of thorium nitrate in the gel-forming mixture, the rate of increase of viscosity decreases considerably (*cf.* Fig. 1). The curves for 0.318 g. and 0.33 g. are rapidly rising ones and they become definitely S-shaped when the amount of thorium nitrate is increased to 0.36 g., 0.39 g., and 0.42 g. indicating the autocatalytic process in gelation. The last curve (0.42 g.) is a flat "S" showing only small increase in viscosity with time. The retardation of the gelation process as indicated by the curves given in Fig. 1 can be attributed to the peptising action of the thorium ions whereby the density of charge on the micelles and their degree of dispersity are increased. Assuming that the viscosity of the gel-forming mixtures is a function of the size of the micelles and their degree of hydration, the decrease in viscosity at any given interval of time with increase of thorium nitrate in the mixtures, shows that a high density of charge is associated with low degree of hydration. Previous workers have also come to the same conclusion regarding the effect of the metal ions.

FIG. 3.

Effect of temperature.

Effect of the addition of increasing amounts of arsenic acid (Fig. 2) is to accelerate the rate of increase of viscosity of the gel-forming mixtures with time. Since increasing amounts of arsenic acid are added to the same amount of thorium nitrate, it is reasonable to expect that the amount of thorium arsenate formed in the gel-forming mixture is increased thereby. Such an increase may cause an increase either in the number of the micelles or their size or both. It also effects a decrease in the concentration of the peptising ions which, in turn, causes a decrease in the density of charge and an increase in the degree of hydration of the micelles. The latter effect suggests that the addition of increasing amounts of arsenic acid causes preferably an increase in the size of the micelles.

Addition of extra amounts of solutions of KCl and BaCl₂ increases the rate of increase of viscosity with time (curves not shown). These results are expected normally because such an addition would accelerate the rate of coagulation of the micelles or probably the micelles formed in the presence of extra amounts of electrolytes would not have a large density of charge. A comparison of the effect produced by adding the same volume of solutions of KCl and BaCl₂ of the same normality gives the expected result that BaCl₂ effects greater increase in viscosity than KCl.

Addition of alcohols and glycerine decreases the rate of increase of viscosity with time and this effect is enhanced as the amount of non-electrolyte added to the mixture is increased. It is very marked in the case of glycerine which practically completely retards large changes in viscosity. This behaviour of non-electrolytes is similar to that observed by previous workers. The observed retarding effect may be due to an increase in the density of charge on the micelles either on account of the diminution of the dielectric constant of the medium or on account of the preferential adsorption of the peptising agent by the micelles in presence of the non-electrolytes. However, it is also possible that the rate of coagulation of the sol of the gel-forming substance is decreased on account of an increase in viscosity on the addition of non-electrolytes. The last mentioned effect seems to be important as it has been observed that the various curves (not shown) are coincident in the early stages.

The rise in temperature causes a decrease in the rate of increase of viscosity during gel-formation. This effect is considerable as evident from Fig. 3 which shows that the rapidly rising curve at 35° becomes almost flat by a rise in temperature by 3°. Prasad and Desai (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 3) and Prakash (*ibid.*, 1932, 9, 193) also observed a decrease in the time of setting of thorium arsenate gels with rise in temperature. This effect of temperature is peculiar to the gels of thorium arsenate as in

FIG. 4.

all other inorganic gels it has been found that the time of setting increases on increasing the temperature. Attempts are being made to find an explanation for this peculiarity.

The gels prepared from thorium nitrate and potassium arsenate are very different in character from those obtained by the use of arsenic acid. The former are invariably turbid but their turbidity decreases as larger amounts of thorium nitrate are used. This observation again points to the great peptising action of thorium ions. The viscosity-time curves obtained with smaller quantities of potassium arsenate show very small changes in viscosity. When the quantity of potassium arsenate is increased

these curves first become S-shaped and then rapidly rising ones. These results are in accord with the discussion given above.

C O N C L U S I O N .

The results given above show that the viscosity method can be employed to study the process of gelation and comparable results can be obtained to show the changes which occur in the process when the condition of the formation of gels, such as the concentration of the constituents of gel-forming mixtures, the temperature, the presence of non-electrolytes, electrolytes and others, are altered. The formation of thorium arsenate gels under various circumstances given above is shown by this method to be a continuous process and no indications have been obtained to bear out the suggestion of any separate existence of different stages involved in the process of gelation.

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